

Mangroves CHI with stressor extracts dataset

Column name	Description
ORIG_FID	Feature ID
x	x coordinate of the grid cell
y	y coordinate of the grid cell
CHI_deterministic	Deterministic cumulative human impact score
Pop_CHI	CHI contribution from population density
OC_CHI	CHI contribution from organic chemical pollution
Nutrpo_CHI	CHI contribution from nutrient pollution
Nighti_CHI	CHI contribution from nighttime light
CO2_CHI	CHI contribution from carbon emissions
Urban_CHI	CHI contribution from urban areas
Touris_CHI	CHI contribution from tourism sites
Road_CHI	CHI contribution from road density
Powpla_CHI	CHI contribution from power plants
Port_CHI	CHI contribution from port locations
Pipe_CHI	CHI contribution from oil pipelines
Oilsto_CHI	CHI contribution from oil storage locations
Oilpal_CHI	CHI contribution from oil palm plantations
Mining_CHI	CHI contribution from mining points
GPW_CHI	CHI contribution from plastic waste sites
Dam_CHI	CHI contribution from dam locations
Crop_CHI	CHI contribution from cropland
Aqua_CHI	CHI contribution from aquaculture ponds
country	Country name for the grid cell

CHI on mangroves in Southeast Asia dataset

Column name	Description
ORIG_FID	Feature ID
x	x coordinate of the grid cell
y	y coordinate of the grid cell
CHI_deterministic	Deterministic cumulative human impact score
country	Country name for the grid cell
dynamic CHI	Estimates of CHI after incorporating uncertainty
posterior_variance	Posterior variance of CHI
xi	Latent variable xi